

University of Idaho

Deep-Time Knowledge Base: Enrich Machine-Readable Semantics and Support Data-Driven Discovery

Xiaogang (Marshall) Ma (max@uidaho.edu), Chris McVickar, Jiyin Zhang, Xiang Que, Amruta Kale
Department of Computer Science, University of Idaho, Moscow, ID 83844, USA

Background

- In data-intensive geoscience research, geoscientists often face the challenges caused by data heterogeneity
- Geologic time can be used as a common reference to connect the data silos
- Heterogeneous geologic time standards are used in data records of different disciplines
- In the open data environment, We need a Web-based and machine-readable knowledge base of deep time to automate data access and synthesis in executable workflows

Data Sources

rruff.info

mindat.org

paleobiodb.org

onegeology.org

mrdata.usgs.gov

earthchem.org

rcsb.org

timescalecreator.org

...

Computer Technologies

- RDF and OWL building the conceptual framework of geologic time
- SKOS for encoding the global, national and regional geologic time standards
- SPARQL for querying the knowledge base
- Interfaces to R and Python

Ongoing and Future Work

We are leveraging the deep-time knowledge base in executable workflows for data-intensive research

- We are currently building several visualized data exploration functions and conducting experimental data analyses

A golden spike map

Golden spike of Cenozoic (66Ma)

Golden spike of Mesozoic (252Ma)

Golden spike of Paleozoic (539Ma)

144 Ma

Scan QR code to try the demo

- We will collaborate with colleagues in the field of mineralogy, paleontology, and paleoclimatology to apply the knowledge base and build use cases of data-driven discovery

WEBSITE: DEEPTIMEKB.ORG ; TWITTER: [@DTKB11](https://twitter.com/DTKB11)

Output 1: A new structure for tracking version information in the deep-time knowledge graph

- A novel structure for version control in the deep-time knowledge graph
- Existing ontologies and vocabularies are fully reused and accredited
- The knowledge base service allows tracking version information of concepts and attributes in deep time

Here Jurassic (J) and the age at the base boundary of Jurassic are used as an example

Output 2: Expand to regional geologic time scales and incorporate temporal topology

- Built knowledge graphs for a list of regional geologic time scales and included them in the knowledge base service
- Embedded temporal topology of Time Ontology into the knowledge graphs and built an R package to support reasoning

Primary relationships in temporal topology

Roadmap for applications

Output 3: A comprehensive review of studies on knowledge graph in geoscience

- Discussed workflows and best practices of geoscience knowledge graph construction
- Summarized exemplar knowledge graph applications in geoscience data curation and analysis
- Analyzed challenges and trends of knowledge graphs in data-intensive geosciences

Perspective from geoscientists: A top-down approach for knowledge graph construction and implementation

Experience from real-world practices: A workflow for constructing and implementing knowledge graphs

DOI of related publications: 10.1016/j.cageo.2022.105082; 10.1016/j.cageo.2020.104620; 10.1016/j.cageo.2018.03.004; 10.1007/s12145-017-0304-8; 10.1007/s12145-013-0110-x; 10.1016/j.cageo.2011.07.018

Acknowledgement: This presentation is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 1835717.